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Terahertz COMING: from Channel to coMmunications aNd sensinG, cross near-and far-field

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饮水思源 · 爱国荣校

“Progress in science depends on new **techniques**, new **discoveries** and new **ideas**, probably in that **order**.” - Sydney Brenner (Nobel prize 2002)

Y.-J. Lyu 吕叶鉴 博士后	M.-X. Li 李铭祥 博士后	W.-J. Gao 高惟君 博士后	Y.-B. Li 李元博 博士5年级	Z.-F. Hu 胡植峰 博士5年级	Y.-Q. Wang 王依勤 博士4年级	Z.-D. Hu 胡正东 博士4年级	H.-Y. Shen 沈和音 博士3年级	Z.-T. Fang 方子童 博士2年级	W.-Q. Zhao 赵文祺 博士1年级	M. L. Li 李美琳 博士1年级	Z.-P. Yin 殷哲朴 博士1年级
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I. F. Akyildiz, J. M. Jornet, and C. Han, “Terahertz Band: Next Frontier for Wireless Communications”, *Elsevier Physical Communication Journal*, 2014 (second highest cited paper on THz comm)

■ Quest for connection of **everything, anywhere, all-time**

■ **More Devices:**

More than 500 billion mobile-connected devices by 2030, forecasted by Cisco

■ **Faster Connections:**

Wireless Terabit-per-second (Tbps) links will become a reality in 6G 2030 and beyond

I. F. Akyildiz, C. Han*, Z.-F. Hu, S. Nie, J. Jornet, “Terahertz Band Communication: An Old Problem Revisited and Research Directions for the Next Decade (Invited Paper)”, *IEEE Transactions on Communications*, 2022

K. Liu, Y. Feng, C. Han*, Z. Chen*, B. Zhang, et. al., "High-Speed 0.22 THz Communication System with 84 Gbps for Real-Time Uncompressed 8K Video Transmission of Live Events", *Nature Communications*, 2024

Sports event broadcasting: ultra-low latency, uncompressed 8K ultra HD video in FISU'2023 (Olympics for world university students)

- Real-time transmission rate exceeding **84 Gbps**
- Distance coverage of over **1.2 kilometer**

THz Channel Measurement and Characteristics

Up to 400GHz VNA-based channel sounder

Parameter	Value
Frequency	100-400 GHz
Antenna gain	25-27 dBi
Antenna beamwidth	8°
Noise floor	-180 dB
Dynamic range	57 dB
Azimuth scan	0 - 360°
Elevation scan	-75° - 40°
Angular resolution	1°
Max path length	120 m
Height	1.8 - 3 m

World-leading specs

- ❖ Frequency and bandwidth: over 300+ GHz and 30 GHz wide
- ❖ Measurable distance: 120m

Ceyear 思仪

“We adopt a 260-400 GHz channel measurement platform that consists of radio frequency (RF) fronts supported by a Ceyear 3672C VNA.”

140-220-350 GHz correlation-based communication and channel system

Parameter	Value
Frequency	100-400 GHz
Bandwidth	2 GHz
Antenna gain	25-27 dBi
Antenna beamwidth	8°
Noise floor	<-150 dB
Dynamic range	50 dB
Azimuth scan	0° - 360°
Elevation scan	-75° - 40°
Tx/Rx distance	>200 m
Measurement speed	<2 ms per CIR
Height	1.6 - 3 m

World-leading specs

- ❖ Measurable distance: > 400 m
- ❖ Support mobile applications
- ❖ Measurement speed: < 2 ms per CIR

“We adopt a THz channel measurement platform that consists of PXIe chassis supported by National Instruments.”

THz Time Domain Spectroscopy (THz-TDS)

MenloSystems

Parameter	Value
Dynamic range	> 100 dB
Bandwidth	> 6 THz
Scan range	> 850 ps
Spectral resolution	< 1.2 GHz

World-leading specs

- ❖ Large bandwidth > 6 THz
- ❖ Large dynamic range > 100 dB
- ❖ Large scan range > 850 ps
- ❖ High spectral resolution < 1.2 GHz

Our Measurement Campaigns - Indoor

Meeting room,
130-143 GHz, 201-209 GHz

Office room,
130-143 GHz, 201-209 GHz

Data center, 130-140 GHz

L-shaped hallway,
306-321 GHz, 356-371 GHz

Long corridor, 306-321 GHz

Lobby, 306-321 GHz

Patio, 306-321 GHz

Y. Li, Y. Wang, Y. Chen, Z. Yu, and **C. Han**, “300 GHz Channel Measurement and Characterization in the Atrium of a Building”, in *EuCAP*, 2023.

University street, 306-321 GHz, 356-371 GHz

Y. Wang, Y. Li, Y. Chen, Z. Yu, and **C. Han**, “Terahertz Channel Measurement and Analysis on a University Campus Street”, *IEEE ICC*, 2023.

THz picocell, 219-221 GHz

Y. Li, Y. Wang, Z. Chen, Y. Chen, Z. Yu, and **C. Han**, “Correlation-based Channel Measurement and Link-Level Analysis for THz Picocells on a University Street”, *IEEE VTC*, 2024.

THz UMi, 219-221 GHz

Y. Li, Y. Lyu, and **C. Han**, "Correlation-based Channel Measurement for THz UMi over 400m Coverage", *IEEE GC*, 2024. arXiv preprint: 2408.15772

• Dominant attenuation effects in atmospheric layers

- In **troposphere**
 - FSPL
 - Molecular absorption caused by water vapor
 - Rayleigh scattering
 - Mie scattering
- In **stratosphere**
 - FSPL
 - Molecular absorption caused by oxygen
- In **ionosphere** and **outer space**
 - FSPL

FSPL: Free-space path loss
$$L_{spr} = \left(\frac{4\pi fc}{d} \right)^2$$

Terahertz Wireless Channel Dataset

Welcome to visit Terahertz wireless channel dataset based on world-leading channel sounders and simulators: <https://sites.ji.sjtu.edu.cn/twcd/>

Terahertz Wireless Channel Dataset

15+ Scenarios

up to 400 GHz Measuring frequency

60w+ CIR data

THz Channel Measurement

The wireless propagation channel is the medium over which transportation of the signals from the transmitter (Tx) to the receiver (Rx) occurs, and as a consequence, channel properties determine the ultimate performance limits of wireless communications, as well as the performance of specific transmission schemes and transceiver architectures. Since wireless channels are the foundation for designing a wireless communication system in the new spectrum and new environments, it is imperative to study the THz radio propagation channels for 6G future wireless communications. Studying wireless channel features relies on the physical channel measurements with channel sounders. The characteristics of the wireless channel are then analyzed based on the measurement results for developing channel models. Channel models capture the nature of wave propagation with reasonable complexity and allow the fair comparison of different algorithms, designs and performance in wireless networks. Channel characteristics in the THz band might be different from those of the mmWave and cmWave bands. Due to the smaller wavelength, waves in the THz band interact through reflection, scattering and diffraction with smaller environmental structures, such as surface roughness with sub-millimeter dimensions, and suffer from absorption and scattering by molecules and tiny particles in the atmosphere. They therefore exhibit unique behaviors compared with those in lower frequency bands. Though methodologies of channel modeling in the THz band inherit from those in the mmWave band, a specific modeling and parameterization of THz channels is still required in order to accurately characterize THz wave propagation for diverse application scenarios for 6G.

The channel measurement platform supports the frequency ranging from 260 GHz to 400 GHz. The system is composed of the Tx module, the Rx module, and the Ceyear 3672C VNA. The VNA generates radio frequency (RF) and local oscillator (LO) sources. The signals from RF and LO sources are multiplied by 27 and 24, respectively. As a result, the transmitted signal reaches the carrier frequencies ranging from 260 GHz to 400 GHz, and the mixed intermediate frequency (IF) signal has the frequency of 7.6 MHz. The IF signals at Tx and Rx modules are both sent back to the VNA, and the transfer function of the channel is calculated as the ratio of the two frequency responses.

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Measurement Scenario and Results

1. Corridor

The corridor is on the second floor of the Langlin Building in Shanghai Jiao Tong University. Both sides of the corridor are furnished with glass walls. To connect pieces of glass together, metal pillars are installed on the glass walls. The separation distance between the consecutive metal pillars is around 1.26 m. Laboratory rooms lie on both sides of the corridor, furnished with wooden doors with width around 0.93 m. Moreover, an around 7 m long segment of the walls on the southern side is covered with wood. Besides, the concrete walls are on both ends of the corridor.

Frequency	306.311 GHz
# Position	105°7'1, 104°5'1
# CIR	2471875
Distance	5.1-131.2 m
Tx height	2.5 m
Rx height	2 m

Y. Li, Y. Wang, X. Chen, Z. Yu, and C. Han, "Channel Measurement and Analysis in an Indoor Corridor Scenario at 300-GHz," in Proc. of IEEE International Conference on Communications (ICC), pp. 1-6, Jun. 2022.

2. Lobby

The measurement campaign is conducted in the lobby on the ground floor of the Langlin building on the SJTU campus. The major area is the rectangular measurement in front of the stairs with more than 500 m², including a glass revolving gate on the north, four symmetrically distributed pillars in the middle, and one LED screen on the south. Two narrow corridors are extended to the west and east, respectively.

Frequency	306.311 GHz
# Position	105°7'16, 104°5'14
# CIR	2171875
Distance	1.1-118.9 m
Tx height	2.5 m
Rx height	2 m

3. L-shaped hallway

The hallway is on the second floor of the Langlin Building in Shanghai Jiao Tong University. The scenario mainly consists of two perpendicular corridors, connected by a corner. The long corridor is 2.17 m wide and 32.33 m long, including two 3 m long extensions at both ends. Indented offices are distributed along the corridor, whose depth is about 0.8 m with doors closed. The other corridor is 7 m wide which extends all the way to the left end.

Frequency	306.311, 156.155 GHz
# Position	105°7'16, 104°5'14
# CIR	2711875
Distance	1.1-122.8 m
Tx height	3 m
Rx height	1.75 m

Y. Wang, Y. Li, X. Chen, Z. Yu, and C. Han, "3.3 THz Channel Measurement and Analysis in an L-shaped Indoor Hallway," in Proc. of IEEE International Conference on Communications (ICC), pp. 1-6, Jun. 2022.

- 🚫 **Challenge:** in direction-scan sounding, **signal phases instability** and large data sizes problems
- 🚫 **Our solution:** direction-scan sounding (**DSS**)-oriented **SAGE (DSS-o-SAGE)** algorithm, using a maximum likelihood estimator (MLE) is derived taking into account the scanning-direction-dependent phases with a coarse-to-fine process

Scanning-direction-dependent signal phase

Coarse-to-fine estimation with partial data

Higher estimation accuracy than existing methods

Y.-B. Li, **C. Han***, Y. Chen, Z. Yu, and X. Yin, "DSS-o-SAGE: Direction-Scan Sounding-Oriented SAGE Algorithm for Channel Parameter Estimation in mmWave and THz Bands", *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, 2024

- ⊗ **Challenge:** realistic clusters appear in different shapes in different environments, for which a flexible and general distance metric is needed for MPC clustering
- ⊗ **Our solution:** a general framework of Mahalanobis-distance metric with distance metric learning, including delay and angle factors

$$\begin{aligned} dist(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_j) &= \|\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j\|_{\mathbf{A}} \\ &= \sqrt{(\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j)^T \mathbf{A} (\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{x}_l = \begin{bmatrix} \tau_l \\ \sin \theta_{T,l} \cos \phi_{T,l} \\ \sin \theta_{T,l} \sin \phi_{T,l} \\ \cos \theta_{T,l} \\ \sin \theta_{R,l} \cos \phi_{R,l} \\ \sin \theta_{R,l} \sin \phi_{R,l} \\ \cos \theta_{R,l} \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{A} \text{ is a real semidefinite matrix}$$

Mahalanobis-distance metric

Machine learning-based distance metric learning

Better clustering performance than existing MCD

🚫 **Challenge:** existing path loss models do **not accurately capture NLoS propagation**

🚫 **Our solution:** a **generalized L-shaped scenario model with a new distance measure**, statistical model of large- and small-scale parameters, **80% more accurate than the AB model**

Generalized L-shaped scenario model

Flow chart of the hybrid channel modeling method

Traditional Euclidean distance and $\alpha\beta$ (AB) model fit		Proposed projection distance and modified-AB model fit	
○ Row 1, Euclidean distance - PL_{best} measurement	○ Row 1, Proposed projection distance - PL_{best} measurement	○ Row 1, PL_{best} M-AB fit: $\alpha_{\text{NLoS}}=6.67, \beta_{\text{NLoS}}=64.19$	○ Row 1, PL_{best} M-AB fit: $\alpha_{\text{NLoS}}=6.67, \beta_{\text{NLoS}}=64.19$
◇ Row 1, Euclidean distance - PL_{omni} measurement	◇ Row 1, Proposed projection distance - PL_{omni} measurement	◇ Row 1, PL_{omni} M-AB fit: $\alpha_{\text{NLoS}}=5.61, \beta_{\text{NLoS}}=69.34$	◇ Row 1, PL_{omni} M-AB fit: $\alpha_{\text{NLoS}}=5.61, \beta_{\text{NLoS}}=69.34$
○ Row 1, PL_{omni} AB fit: $\alpha_{\text{NLoS}}=27.81, \beta_{\text{NLoS}}=230.74$	○ Row 1, PL_{omni} AB fit: $\alpha_{\text{NLoS}}=27.81, \beta_{\text{NLoS}}=230.74$	○ Row 1, PL_{omni} AB fit: $\alpha_{\text{NLoS}}=27.81, \beta_{\text{NLoS}}=230.74$	○ Row 1, PL_{omni} AB fit: $\alpha_{\text{NLoS}}=27.81, \beta_{\text{NLoS}}=230.74$
○ Row 2, Euclidean distance - PL_{best} measurement	○ Row 2, Proposed projection distance - PL_{best} measurement	○ Row 2, PL_{best} M-AB fit: $\alpha_{\text{NLoS}}=6.73, \beta_{\text{NLoS}}=61.79$	○ Row 2, PL_{best} M-AB fit: $\alpha_{\text{NLoS}}=6.73, \beta_{\text{NLoS}}=61.79$
◇ Row 2, Euclidean distance - PL_{omni} measurement	◇ Row 2, Proposed projection distance - PL_{omni} measurement	◇ Row 2, PL_{omni} M-AB fit: $\alpha_{\text{NLoS}}=6.40, \beta_{\text{NLoS}}=60.66$	◇ Row 2, PL_{omni} M-AB fit: $\alpha_{\text{NLoS}}=6.40, \beta_{\text{NLoS}}=60.66$
○ Row 2, PL_{omni} AB fit: $\alpha_{\text{NLoS}}=33.28, \beta_{\text{NLoS}}=317.68$	○ Row 2, PL_{omni} AB fit: $\alpha_{\text{NLoS}}=33.28, \beta_{\text{NLoS}}=317.68$	○ Row 2, PL_{omni} AB fit: $\alpha_{\text{NLoS}}=33.28, \beta_{\text{NLoS}}=317.68$	○ Row 2, PL_{omni} AB fit: $\alpha_{\text{NLoS}}=33.28, \beta_{\text{NLoS}}=317.68$

Modified alpha-beta path loss model

From raw data to 3GPP standards - a **complete and real-time data post-processing** including estimation, clustering, characterization, and modeling

方向扫描

实际信道

Parameter Settings

Scenario parameters

Data directory: C:\Users\yuanboli\C

Scenario number: 1

Tx index: 1 Rx index: 1

Frequency band [GHz]: 306 ~ 321

Calibration status: Yes

Noise-elimination parameters

Dynamic range [dB]: 30

Noise floor [dB]: -145

DBSCAN clustering parameters

ToA scaler: 5

Maximum distance: 0.18

Minimum points: 5

Channel Data Processing

Processing results

Plot PDAP

Plot clustering result

Show channel characteristics

	Rx point 1	Rx point 2	Rx point 3	R
Distance [m]	5.0590	6.0990	7.0560	
PL [dB]	93.3523	93.8836	94.9646	
SF [dB]	-0.4108	0.2775	0.1472	
KF [dB]	21.3333	16.2144	17.1035	
DS [ns]	3.4857	5.9838	5.9977	
ASA [degree]	23.7456	28.4141	28.1972	
ESA [degree]	5.6028	6.6297	6.4883	
Cluster number	2.0000	7.0000	5.0000	
CDS [ns]	0.6060	1.4766	0.7288	
CASA [degree]	7.1964	4.1065	5.3846	
CESA [degree]	4.6488	4.7207	4.2775	

	LoS	NLoS
PL [dB]	1.502	3.70
SF [dB]	uSF=0.021801, sSF=0.82008	uSF
KF [dB]	uKF=15.494, sKF=2.5979	uKF
DS [dBs]	uDS=-7.8585, sDS=0.20705	uDS
ASA [dBdegree]	uASA=1.4891, sASA=0.090973	uASA
ESA [dBdegree]	uESA=0.87307, sESA=0.049363	uESA
Cluster number	uCNum=6.1429	uC
CDS [dBs]	uCDS=3.3775	uCI
CASA [dBdegree]	uCASA=4.8053	uCA
CESA [dBdegree]	uCESA=3.7353	uCE

离、频率、环境
择性

生分析

散射效应明显

Shadow fading (SF): additional loss caused by blockage; mostly calculated as the deviation of path loss to path loss models

- ❖ Severer shadow fading in NLoS
- ❖ Mostly lower than 1 in indoor scenarios

Blockage is an issue to address, maybe need reflecting surfaces

(a) Indoor scenarios

(b) Outdoor scenarios

K-factor (KF): the power ratio between the strongest path and other paths

- ❖ Generally larger KF in outdoor scenarios
- ❖ Mostly very large in the THz band (>10 dB), indicating high sparsity

Still having multipath (less than 10 MPCs), sparsity is high

- Delay spread (DS): the power dispersion in the temporal domain**
- ❖ Generally larger DS in outdoor scenarios
 - ❖ Smaller DS for higher frequencies
 - ❖ Typically around 5~30 ns in indoor scenarios
 - ❖ 5-60 ns in outdoor scenarios

Dominant paths are observed

- (a) Indoor, omnidirectional results;
- (b) Indoor, directional results;
- (c) Outdoor omnidirectional results;
- (d) Outdoor, directional results.

Angular spread (AS): the power dispersion in the spatial domain

- ❖ Close AS in indoor and outdoor scenarios
- ❖ Typically around 10-60° for ASA and ASD

Dominant directions are observed

a) ASA; (b) ASD;
 (c) ESA; (d) ESD.

Rain

Rainfall rate : 20 mm/h

- Water droplets above 0 °C, whose radius is between 0.25 mm and 1.5 mm.

11 dB/km

Cloud

- Water droplets above 0 °C, whose radius is between 1 μm and 30 μm .

7 dB

Fog

Visibility: 100m

- Tiny water droplets or ice crystals with the size of generally 1-20 μm .

1.4 dB/km

Dust

Visibility: 100m

- Sand particles with a scale of 0.05~150 μm .

1.2 dB/km

Frequency: 300 GHz, wavelength: 1mm

**Shorter wavelength leads to severer scattering,
significantly better than FSO though**

Channel modeling formulated as a channel distribution learning problem

❖ THz channel can be represented as

$$h(\tau) = \sum_{l=0}^{L-1} \alpha_l e^{j\phi_l} \delta(\tau - \tau_l),$$

❖ Every MPC can be represented by

$$\mathbf{x}_l = [\alpha_l, \tau_l, \theta_l, \phi_l]$$

- L : number of multipath components (MPC)
- α_l : path gain of the l^{th} path
- τ_l : delay of the l^{th} path
- θ_l : azimuth angle of arrival for the l^{th} path
- ϕ_l : elevation angle of arrival for the l^{th} path

❖ THz channel can be characterized by

$$\mathbf{X} = [\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2, \dots, \mathbf{x}_L]$$

❖ The channel modeling problem is exploited by **learning the distribution of channel parameters** denoted by p_r , which is difficult to be analytically represented

Z.-D. Hu, Y.-B. Li, and C. Han*, "Transfer Learning Enabled Transformer based Generative Adversarial Networks (TT-GAN) for Terahertz Channel Modeling and Generating", *Nature Communications Engineering*, 2024

- A generative adversarial network (GAN) is exploited to generate channel parameters
- To improve the accuracy, a transformer structure with self-attention is incorporated in T-GAN
- A transfer learning is designed to solve the mismatch between the T-GAN and measurement in a new scenario

Z.-D. Hu, Y.-B. Li, and C. Han*, "Transfer Learning Enabled Transformer based Generative Adversarial Networks (TT-GAN) for Terahertz Channel Modeling and Generating", *Nature Communications Engineering*, 2024

Delay spread

- ❖ When the dataset size is **lower than 9**, the CDFs for TT-GAN fall outside the 99% confidence interval of the measurement CDF.

Angular spread

- ❖ The CDFs of angular spread for TT-GAN diverge from the measurement CDF as the dataset size decreases to **less than 5**

A minimum of **9 data points** from a new environment could guarantee high accuracy of the TT-GAN

Terahertz Channel Models

Evolution of Channel Modeling Methods

C. Han, and Y. Chen, "Propagation Modeling for Wireless Communications in the Terahertz Band", *IEEE Communications Magazine*, 2018

C. Han, and Y. Chen, "Propagation Modeling for Wireless Communications in the Terahertz Band", *IEEE Communications Magazine*, 2018

Method 1: Deterministic channel modeling

Site-specific-> Require details
of the environment
geometric information

High accuracy and high
computing complexity

Low adaptability

Method 2: Statistical channel modeling

Not site-specific -> no need
for geometric information

Channel statistics of a type of
scenarios based on
measurements or simulation

Relatively low accuracy but
fast channel generation

Method 3: Hybrid channel modeling

Combine two or more
deterministic channel
modeling approaches

Tradeoff among accuracy,
complexity and adaptability

Y. Chen, Y. Li, **C. Han***, Z. Yu, and G. Wang, "Channel Measurement and Ray-Tracing-Statistical Hybrid Modeling for Low-Terahertz Indoor Communications," *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, 2021

⊗ A hybrid channel model for THz indoor meeting room

$$h(\tau, \theta, f) = h_{RT}(\tau, \theta, f) + h_s(\tau, \theta, f)$$

RT-statistical hybrid channel = **Deterministic part** + **Statistical part** → **Wave-particle duality**

⊗ Deterministic part $h_{RT}(\tau, \theta, f)$:

$$h_{RT}(\tau, \theta, f) = A_t(\vec{\phi}_{LoS})\alpha_{LoS}(f)\delta(\tau - \tau_{LoS})\delta(\theta - \theta_{LoS}) + \sum_{l=0}^{L_{RT}} A_t(\vec{\phi}_{l,0})\alpha_{l,0}(f)\delta(\tau - \tau_{l,0})\delta(\theta - \theta_{l,0})$$

❖ **Generated by ray-tracing**

❖ LoS path and the specular reflection path in wall-reflection clusters

⊗ Statistical part:

$$h_s(\tau, \theta, f) = \sum_{l=0}^{L_{RT}} \sum_{p=-Q_l, p \neq 0}^{P_l} A_t(\vec{\phi}_{l,p})\alpha_{l,p}(f)\delta(\tau - \tau_{l,p})\delta(\theta - \theta_{l,p}) + \sum_{q=0}^{L_s} \sum_{s=-Q_l}^{P_l} A_t(\vec{\phi}_{l,s})\alpha_{l,s}(f)\delta(\tau - \tau_{l,s})\delta(\theta - \theta_{l,s})$$

❖ **Statistically generated** based on the measured cluster statistics

❖ The other intra-cluster MPCs in wall-reflection clusters and non-dominant NLoS clusters

At 130-143 GHz

CDF: Delay spread

CDF: Angular spread

(a) Meeting room for THz channel measurements.

(b) Overview of the meeting room and measurement deployment.

THz Communication and Sensing Design Guidelines

饮水思源 · 爱国荣校

C. Han, W. Gao, N. Yang, and J. M. Jornet, "Molecular Absorption Effect: A Double-edged Sword of Terahertz Communications," *IEEE Wireless Communications*, 2022

Spectral windows created by molecular absorption effects

Each window has multi-GHz BW, sensitive to f, d, env.

Distance-adaptive multi-wideband communication

C. Han, A. O. Bicen, and I. F. Akyildiz, "Multi-Wideband Waveform Design for Distance-Adaptive Wireless Communications in the Terahertz Band", *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, 2016

Naturally high security for THz communications

- High path loss
- High directivity

Covert Region due to
High Directionality

Reduce
insecure
region

Alice

Bob

Insecure Region

Covert Region due to
High Path Loss

Spectrum-based idea

- Distance-adaptively selected carrier frequencies, to exploit the **THz molecular absorption effects**

W. Gao, Y. Chen, C. Han*, and Z. Chen, "Distance-Adaptive Absorption Peak Modulation (DA-APM) for Terahertz Covert Communications", *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, 2020

⊗ Decreasing Tx power reduces power at Bob and Willie **equally**

⊗ Molecular absorption peak modulation reduces power at farther Willie **significantly larger** than at Bob

- ⊗ **K-factor mostly very large (>10 dB), indicating high sparsity**
- ⊗ **Rather than number of antennas, the spatial degree of freedom is constrained by the channel rank**
- ⊗ **However, more degree of freedom is available in the near-field**
 - Rayleigh distance as far/near-field Boundary

Boundary: Rayleigh distance $D_{ray} = \frac{2S^2}{\lambda}$

- **The communication distance $D \gg D_{ray} \rightarrow$ The planar-wave assumption is valid**
- **Otherwise, e.g., $D < D_{ray} \rightarrow$ The spherical-wave propagation needs to be considered**

Y.-Q. Wang, **C. Han***, S. Sun, and J. Zhang, “Cross Far- and Near-Field Channel Measurement and Modeling in Extremely Large-scale Movable Antenna Array Systems”, arXiv 2405.16893, May 2024. shorter version in *IEEE Communications Letters*, 2024

Case	Far-field	More or less	Near-field
Antenna type	16x16 UPA	32x32 UPA	64x64 UPA
Element spacing	0.5 mm	0.5 mm	0.5 mm
Raleigh distance	0.2250 m	0.9610 m	3.9690 m
Tx-Rx distance	0.86 m	0.86 m	0.86 m

Multiple-input-single-output channel, 260-320 GHz

L. Yan, Y. Chen, **C. Han*** and J. Yuan, "Joint Inter-Path and Intra-Path Multiplexing for Terahertz Widely-Spaced Multi-Subarray Hybrid Beamforming Systems," *IEEE Transactions on Communications*, 2022

④ **Widely-spaced multi-subarray (WSMS) hybrid beamforming design, to **manipulate** the boundary**

- Multipath components, e.g., LoS and NLoS → **Inter-path multiplexing gain**
- **Widely-spaced subarrays**
 - D_{ray} of the whole array is larger than D
 - PWM within one subarray and SWM among widely-spaced subarrays
 - Multiplexing exists within one multipath, i.e., **intra-path multiplexing**
- **The total multiplexing gain is kN_p** , where the inter-path multiplexing is N_p and the intra-path multiplexing is k

④ **The spatial multiplexing gain of WSMS is substantially improved to k times!**

Focused beam is a tightly concentrated EM wave with a small spot size, commonly used in applications requiring high precision such as imaging and sensing

Rx

Tx

lenses

2 Collimators

scanning stage

VNA

Measured E-field

Ideal E-field

Airy beam describes a non-diffractive EM wave that can accelerate along a **curved trajectory** while maintaining its shape, allowing it to pass around obstacles

Measured E-field

Ideal E-field

Orbital angular momentum (OAM) is an EM wave with a helical phase structure, carrying angular momentum, allowing **mode multiplexing** to increase data capacity in communication

Two significant challenges when designing THz waveform

High Mobility Environment

v_{max}	$f_c = 2$ GHz	$f_c = 60$ GHz	$f_c = 300$ GHz
$v = 1.5$ m/s = 5.5 km/h	10 Hz	300 Hz	1.5 KHz
$v = 3$ m/s = 11 km/h	20 Hz	600 Hz	3 KHz
$v = 30$ m/s = 110 km/h	200 Hz	6 KHz	30 KHz
$v = 150$ m/s = 550 km/h	1 KHz	30 KHz	150 KHz

- Severe Doppler effects
- Doubly-selective channels

Power Amplifiers (PAs)

- Saturated output power decreases
- PAPR requirement tends even stricter

Y. Wu, C. Han, and T. Yang, "DFT-Spread Orthogonal Time Frequency Space Modulation Design for Terahertz Communications", in *Proc. of IEEE GLOBECOM*, 2021

📍 New waveform design to combat severe Doppler effects and PAPR requirements in the THz band

- **DFT-s-OTFS** is proposed by developing a DFT precoding and delay-Doppler domain mapping in front of OTFS modulator
- PAPR of DFT-s-OTFS, OTFS and OFDM is respectively influenced by DFT spreading size, number of symbol, number of subcarriers

C. Han, Y. Wu, Z. Chen, Y. Chen, and G. Wang, "THz ISAC: A Physical-Layer Perspective of Terahertz Integrated Sensing and Communication", *IEEE Communications Magazine*, 2023

Kill two birds with one stone by THz ISAC

- Data rates of 100+ Gbps
- Range/angular resolution of 0.01 m and 1 degree
- Sensing accuracy of 1 mm and 10 milli-degree

Y. Wu, C. Han*, and Z. Chen, "DFT-Spread Orthogonal Time Frequency Space System with Superimposed Pilots for Terahertz Integrated Sensing and Communication", *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, 2023

📡 Sensing integrated DFT-s-OTFS

- Spread the information symbols with DFT precoding along the Doppler axis before OTFS modulation → **reduce PAPR while achieving strong robustness against Doppler effects**
- A pilot symbol is superimposed onto a data symbol → **reduce pilot overhead**

PAPR Performance

Out-of-Band Emission

Range Estimation Accuracy

$f_c = 0.3$ THz, $\Delta f = 1.92$ MHz
target distance = 10 m

- **PAPR**: **DFT-s-OTFS** \approx DFT-s-OFDM < OTFS < OFDM
- **Power amplifier efficiency**: OFDM < OTFS < DFT-s-OFDM \approx **DFT-s-OTFS**
- **Spectral efficiency**: OFDM = DFT-s-OFDM < OTFS = **DFT-s-OTFS**
- **Out-of-band emission**: OTFS \approx **DFT-s-OTFS** < OFDM \approx DFT-s-OFDM
- **BER with strong Doppler effects**: **DFT-s-OTFS** \approx OTFS < DFT-s-OFDM < OFDM
- **Sensing accuracy**: OFDM \approx DFT-s-OFDM < OTFS \approx **DFT-s-OTFS**
- **Receiver complexity**: OFDM = DFT-s-OFDM < **DFT-s-OTFS** = OTFS

- **Reduced PAPR**
- **More robustness to Doppler**
- **Stronger sensing capabilities**

Thanks!

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